

Using Group Work as an Effective Teaching-Learning Strategy to Enhance Nursing Students' Creativities and Participations in Thai Cultural Context

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Abstract— As teaching learning of the nursing innovation course is a nation innovator building in nursing profession, the effective teaching-learning and motivations of the class are worth exploring. This study explored into how the senior nursing students experienced group work in Thai context. The data came from 76 students in nine groups of the course taught. Examination of the class atmosphere and motivations of the students enrolling the course of innovation development in nursing by focus group discussions were obtained. In addition, in-depth interviews with their nine group instructors were carried out for understanding teaching and learning process. A single case, embedded study was completed, which reveals insight and understanding into the manner in which nursing students experience group work assignments and how these experiences contributed to their perception of positive group work outcomes. The major theme extracted in this study was a cognitive outcome via a group learning process, including five stage group process listed as follows: stage 1 Group Assignment, stage 2 Group Organizing, stage 3 Group Performing, stage 4 Close Relationship, and stage 5 Group Celebration. Results proposed a situational group work model, which could be defined as a pattern that identifies crucial situational factors involved with undergraduate nursing student group work, which was student-centered in group work experiences. These findings have strong recommendation for educators to improve group teaching and also to better inform facilitators of group work in the undergraduate nursing classroom.

Keywords— Capstone course, nursing student, group learning, student perceptions, innovation building teaching.

I. INTRODUCTION

Unquestionably the cultural values of social context significantly influence on educational management and outcomes (Mugot, Sumbalan, 2019; Hébert, Hauf, 2015; Lee, Lee, 2012; Bray, 2009). Thai society is a hierarchical system in regard to age, social status, education, occupation, and economic status (Supab, 1994; Cummings, 2002). Influence of socialization affected human behaviors, including communication and treat other people according to Thai social (Burnard, Naiyapatana, 2004). There is a Thai word “*Kreng Jai*” which is close to the word “consideration”. “*Kreng Jai*” implies that one does not want to bother or disturb other person, especially someone who is in social hierarchy, such as

teacher or older person (Wyatt, Promkandorn, 2012; Jongudomkarn, Forgeron, Siripul, Finley, 2012). Students do not ask questions in class because they are afraid of disturbing teacher and other students. Therefore, classroom atmosphere is quiet, no talking between each other which is seen as being respectful to teachers. Additionally, nursing society has its own traditional culture, including rigorous clinical practice, learning from their upper classmate, passive learning style, being conservative, and emphasis on seniority. Therefore, teaching nursing practices in Thai context is more often described as teacher-centered and Thai students as seen as passive learners. Mostly, students' characteristics are humble, dislike to express their opinions in public, and seniority respect. These characteristics would be obstacle factors hindering their opinion expression, criticism of classmates and teachers, learning participation, creativity, and “think outside the box” (Woods, Rosenberg, 2016).

The nursing innovation project course, a compulsory course for the fourth year nursing students, Faculty of Nursing, Khon Kaen University, Thailand is designed to promote each nursing student to be an innovator equipped with creative thinking skill in developing new ideas. After graduation, they are expected to work in nursing profession to provide society with high quality nurse profession resources who can innovatively create and effectively serve people cares in future health work places.

To design teaching-learning style in the nursing innovation project course, learners have to be active, “think outside the box”, and think more creatively to make a difference. Popping up new ideas that lead to the thought producing new products, services, or processes using 5 skills including associating thoughts, questioning, observing, reacting, and testing. Emerging new creativity, learners have to be brave to create a new thing; take risk to make change; be enthusiastic to questioning, observing, reacting, and frequent testing; have perception skill to associate and synthesize information from other disciplines becoming a new thought. Learners must practice to be able to “think outside the box”. Finally, learners

successfully develop nursing innovation which meets course objectives (Jongudomkarn, 2016).

As with nursing professional striving for success, it is the role of nurse educators to work toward continuous improvement in their performance. University nurse educators have also a distinct role in that they not only disseminate knowledge but also produce knowledge related to effective management of teaching and learning. Group work is one of teaching strategies. It is a collaborative learning involving the learners working together to complete a task. Students are assigned to invent or develop a piece of nursing innovation per group. Their group working starts from 1) brain storming for their nursing innovation project 2) reviewing literature related to their innovation 3) designing and drafting their innovation to be 4) inventing the innovation as drafting 5) testing the innovation after getting approval from institutional/organizational ethics committees 6) summarizing the results from the innovation testing 7) making recommendations/comments for innovation improvement 8) Orally presenting their innovation in English and 9) writing final innovation project report in English (Baron, Kerr, 2003; Curseu, Pluut, 2013; Jongudomkarn, 2016).

The successful teaching and learning management in nursing innovation project course, students need to be prepared. Such preparation in the orientation activities can be classified into the categories of (1) innovation-related knowledge, (2) innovation development-related skills, (3) support skills, and (4) accepting the individual differences among their personal and team member characteristics. Innovation-related knowledge involves an understanding of innovation development, nursing theories and concepts. This relates to the subject matter of the courses required for a nursing degree. Innovation development-related skills based on using group project can be made that students learn these skills through these applications in the group work project, and/or extracurricular activities. Support skills (i.e., creativity decision making, communication, teamwork, etc.) consist of skills/abilities that are transferable and relevant across many fields. Here, assigned group work activities can be made that students also learn these skills through work sheet applications in the group work, and/or extracurricular activities as well. Personal and team member characteristics (e.g., being leaded, responsible, mature, enthusiastic, self-motivated, ambitious, self-confident, etc.) are defined as other personal qualities that may be benefited as a potential group member (Chiriac EH, Granström, 2012; Marterella, Rebecca, Aldrich, 2015; Serdyukov, 2017).

Based on each group instructor, group work learning can be playing an important role in the successful implementation in the development of innovation as an important teaching tool when instructing students (Hughes, Jones, 2011). Working in group helps students get closer, decrease the feeling “*Kreng Jai*”, express their true opinions, increase active learning, and be inspired by peer group. Researchers believe in using group work as an effective teaching learning strategy within higher education (Murray, Lonne, 2006).

II. OBJECTIVE

The study was aimed to explore the undergraduate nursing student experiences in group work based on the innovation building course, in terms of the group process emerging, and instructor facilitating. The research question also further clarified and expanded on the narrative of student experiences using fellow group members and instructor for the most satisfied group work outcome as well as the learning of focal course material, and the learning about the group work process.

III. REVIEW LITERATURE

Thailand is located in the Southeast Asia Region. Thai culture beliefs and values the elders, they pay respect to the elders (Jongudomkarn, Phupaibul, Kumhom, Tejagupta, Wacharasin, Deoisres, 2017; NESDP, 2017). Quiet and humble characters or “*Kreng Jai*” were always the characteristics of Thai people. There is no the right word to be translated into Thai word of *Kreng Jai*. This means to be considerate or to feel obligate to do something is thus, a self-reliant stance, *Kreng Jai*, and negative reaction from students to their classroom participation may all be barriers to appropriate learning outcomes in Thai context. *Kreng Jai* is a value that is the essence of a Thai’s character and influences his or her worldview and thus directs behavior (Jongudomkarn, Forgeron, Siripul, Finley, 2012). The issue of “*Kreng jai*” is deep-rooted in Thai society as well as classroom with characteristics of “saving face” and the “big person/little person”, leading to hinder freedom of opinion expression. Teachers are the givers of knowledge, students respect teachers because of their knowledge and wisdom. Students believe that the received knowledge is absolutely correct, it is students’ responsibility to memorize the received knowledge and take note. Good students must not question, doubt, or challenge in the received knowledge because teachers might feel embarrassed, uncomfortable, or ashamed, leading to passive learning style (Wyatt, Promkandorn 2012). Silent is a nature of Thai students. Even when he/she knew the right answer, he/she used to feel that staying silent was preferable to appearing to promote oneself at the expense of his/her friends. In such a classroom culture, speaking out is seen as undesirable. With cultural awareness in student learning, Thai educational management places an importance on moving to a more student-centered and sharing active learning initiative. *The nursing innovation project course* selects group work learning method to enhance student active learning (Brysiewicz, Cassimjee, McInerney, 2002; Chiriac, Granström, 2012; Senior, Howard, 2014). Using group work learning strategy, students have to work together, brain storming, and discuss the course material to help them to meet the main course objective. Teachers or instructors facilitate students by stimulating and monitoring rather than spoon feeding. Active learning helps decreasing various cultural limitations and learners have a sense of ownership toward group project and being important for work success (Kuh, Kinzie, Buckley, Bridges, Hayek, 2006; McKinney, Day,

2012; Senior, Howard, 2014; Brennan, Ryan, Ranga, Broek, Durazzi, Kamphuis, 2014).

IV. ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

Approval was elicited from the faculty's research committee. Research methodology, the students were given a verbal explanation of the objectives of the study and a request for verbal consent was made before obtaining the focus group discussions. Prior to conducting the sessions, researchers also explained the purpose of this study and the researchers' contact details. The students were informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time and were assured that all their responses would be confidential, as the focus group discussion notes were anonymous (Polit, Hungler, 2013).

V. CONTEXT OF THE STUDY

The senior nursing students in the baccalaureate program, Faculty of Nursing, Khon Kaen University spend their first three years in fundamental, community health, pediatric, mental, adult, and elderly nursing, respectively. Their final year they learn nursing administration, midwifery nursing, and the capstone course of nursing innovation development. Throughout the nursing innovation development course, the enrolled students are expected to work in groups. For the course being successful it is thus essential that preparation of good team working of students is made as beneficial as possible.

Khon Kaen University (KKU) consists of 22 faculties and other organizations located in the northeast of Thailand. This country is located in Southeast Asia and 94% of the population is Buddhist. This study was conducted at the Faculty of Nursing, which is among the first nursing faculty of its kind in the country. It is located a six hour drive from Bangkok, the country capital which has a population of 1,821,938 (NESDB, 2019; The Office of Khon Kaen Public Relations).

VI. METHOD

Focus group discussions were employed to collect data. There were two research assistants, who were PhD. students themselves, to engage with the detailed and to get close to an individual's and the group's perspectives (Kayrooz and Trevitt, 2005). This method provided the participants to share their learning experiences freely and identify any gaps or conflicts during the teaching and learning process. Of 156 senior students enrolling in the nursing innovation project course in 2016, 76 volunteer students (50%) participated in the study. In addition, in-depth interviews with nine group instructors represented a teaching and learning process of group working. Each session of focus group interview would last approximately 1.30 hours. The nursing innovation project course offered in the first semester of each academic year for the senior nursing students, students were assigned into 17 groups and each group had one instructor acting as facilitator of learners. This course required majors-only innovation development experience capstones with papers as the main outcomes, where in students did their work assignments as a team group. Triangulation of the focus group interview data

using in-depth interviews with nine group instructors was performed. In addition, member checking was undertaken by 10 student participants to validate the analyzed data (Cho, Trent, 2006). The mean age of student participants was 20.5. The mean self-reported the overall GPA was 2.64 (on 4-point scales). Ninety percent of the students in this course was from local northeastern region and 90 percent was female. Of the students, 81 percent reported their family income as middle class, the rest was lower class.

The focus group discussion with semi-structured approach was conducted in the private, quiet conference room at Faculty of Nursing. Each focus group was conducted by three research assistants who had been well trained in qualitative data collection, therefore minimizing bias, and social desirability artifacts. The research assistants were responsible for 1) conducting interviews, 2) note taking, and 3) facilitating and audio recording. Focus groups discussed the following questions about the course group working: How did you experience group work in an innovation development? How did you interact with peers and the facilitator? How did your group work and its process emerge? Data collection was conducted during the final session of the course, providing students with the opportunity to discuss the range of teaching methods, group assignment, assessment, feedback, learning environments, and strategies experienced during the course of their studies. The focus group data were transcribed by two research assistants and analyzed by the authors (Winlow, Simm, Schaaf, Marvell, 2012). There were 540 statements to be analyzed and 20 key open codes were found. Content analysis approach was obtained.

The study rigor ensured that the findings accurately reflected the students' experiences. Trustworthiness criteria, including credibility, dependability, transferability and conformability were used to establish and document rigor in this study (Streubert, Carpenter, 2011). First of all, various techniques were used to provide evidence of credibility, such as prolonged engagement to better understand the context of the experience (Schwartz-Shea, Yanow, 2012). According to dependability, the obtained data were sufficient quality for analysis and transcription. The researcher team observed every focus group discussions and supervised throughout the transcription process. During focus group interview, research assistants helped to note taking and audio recording. Thick description was used to establish transferability or fittingness. The preliminary data analysis results were presented to 76 faculty members, discussed with 17 instructors and 10 student participants to help improve the accuracy, credibility, and transferability of the study.

VII. RESULTS

The findings revealed that student participant having a good sense of what to expect from the course, reporting learning many innovation building-related skills, and having positive attitudes about the course. Students also stated that the highly structured nature of the course was important for their success but somewhat frustrating. Other important student perceptions were that the course was demanding and time consuming; past courses helped them prepare for the

capstone experience but that there were gaps in this preparation; they learned best via active learning, feedback, and application; they are proud of their course achievements; they impressed with their peer cooperation, instructor and expert giving consultancy. Group working process, initiated students changing their learning goal, dedicating to individual, devoting for group achievement, practicing ‘think outside the box’/creativity, experiencing many different opinions, being responsible together, listening to others, being flexible, being patient to the difference between individuals, practicing coordination. They are engaged in the discipline but are ambiguous about future work in the real world of work. Examples of informants’ opinions were as follows:

“The most importance of best practice is cooperation of peer group, working together to group achievement, don’ feel “*Kreng Jai*”, and consult with instructor...complete the work” (A member of focus group no 1).

“I think what I get most from this subject is creative thinking, in the past nurse emphasized on theory and clinical practice but this subject does not let us “think in the box” but urges us to be brave to think, show our thoughts, have us think a lot...more and more” (A member no 3 of FGD no 4).

“I learn assertiveness skill from peer, courage to express opinions, adopt the strength, long before...I was afraid to speak or express. Right now, I feel self-worth, I am flexible with friend and work....” (A member no 7 of FGD no 8).

A Cognitive Outcome via a Group Learning Process

The key theme to emerge from the data was group learning. All the participants constructed group learning as a cognitive outcome via a group learning process (Fig.I.), which was best achieved through individualistic strategies to learn. There are five stage group process extracted below and each stage has been explained in detail subsequently:

Fig. 1. Overview of Work Group Teaching and Learning Process

Stage 1 Group Assignment: Uncertainty

At the beginning of group teaching and learning, the participant students felt frustrated and unconfident, how they could get the group work done since they had to create the

piece of work by themselves, which was different from what they had learned in the past as the following examples:

“In the past, I got used to learning from lecturing. Even some classes were boring but it could give you very clear idea about what you were going to do next, and you didn’t need to spend a lot of time yourself to figure out, what’s the lecturer wanted us to do?” (A member no 1 of FGD no 2).

“Mostly, we just sat and listened to the lecturer the lecturers gave exactly what they wanted.” (A member no 4 of FGD no 4).

“Usually, we learned in classroom and not so much on discussion.” (A member no 9 of FGD no 6).

“The classes were small, if we couldn’t understand, we could ask during the lectures.” (A member no 5 of FGD no 9).

“Learners got used to learning like they were being spoon fed. Instructor gave lecture in the freshman, sophomore and so on.. this learning style made students adapt themselves to search research articles and develop innovation....” (Instructor 3).

“Mostly students didn’t like to express their opinions, they were afraid of speaking in front of the class, small group helped everyone have a chance to express their ideas, reduce nervousness and *Kreng Jai*...” (Instructor 6).

According to course coordinator assignment to group work, students felt awkward since they did not know each other well. Even though they had been classmates for 3 years, but did not know their classmates characters well. After orientation course, students had to social adjustment in accepting new strangers as group members, they felt unconfident to achieve study goal in nursing innovation development within two months as examples from student participants:

“Although we had studied together as classmates for 3 years but we knew only our group. Classmates that the course coordinator assigned to be in group work seemed to be the strangers, that I had to social adjustment to accept new group members”. (a member no 6 of FGD no 2).

“At first receiving assignment as a group member, I was worried about the task assigned that I had to work together with unfamiliar friends”. (a member no 8 of FGD no 5).

“...At the beginning, I met with new friends that I just knew. I didn’t dare to ask, express my opinions. I felt numb, awkward what to do... where to go”. (a member no 6 of FGD no 7).

“As a matter of fact,...seldom did I and my friends had discussions to a group work. Whereas, uh..., you would be asked to discuss your ideas suddenly here, and sometimes, there was actually nothing to discuss

for those questions...” (A member no 3 of FGD no 8).

“I was worried that different people would have different goals when working together. The group might be failed.” (A member no 2 of FGD no 9).

“I was worried what kind of members we had in a group, I didn’t like it when some were lazy, just sat to listen to others and they didn’t want to do anything...” (A member no 4 of FGD no 9).

Stage 2 Group Organizing: Accepting the Assignment

As anxiously seeing other group works of how they could cooperative working to goal achievement, students had to quickly admit unexpected thing that could happen. Therefore, instructors acting as facilitators had a crucial role in guiding and allocating task for individuals. If the group work members had any cooperative working experiences, this would help group working smoothly in the limited time. During this period of time, every group members tried to work cooperatively and supportively. Instructors helped students decrease the conflicts, express their ideas, and let them working cooperatively as the following examples from student participants and instructors:

“Eventually, we must accept the group to work and accomplish goal. We had to share ideas what innovation we wanted to create. Instructor told us to brainstorm and came up with two choices of innovations, then we would vote which innovation...choice one... or... choice two...then planning to continue our work. It was amazing that some members I had never seen they talked in class, but they spoke in group” (A member no 4 of FGD no 3).

“When it was a group work and we were together, we must admitted and helped in working, bit by bit, having less conflict and got job done, everyone expressed their opinions, they didn’t have to *Kreng Jai* making them did not dare to speak”. (A member no 6 of FGD no 9).

“As the facilitator, we had to understand the characters of group members. We considered what and how we could facilitate them in cooperative working, stimulated everyone to speak out, set a rule and let everyone express their ideas, worked cooperatively. We showed them the schedule plan of working from their upper classmates and let them learn from that to make their own schedule plan”. (Instructor 1).

“From the past experiences, we knew that students had to understand cooperative working in order to help group working fast, so we had to stimulate them to understand in this point, expressed their ideas, and admitted to work cooperatively in the short period”. (Instructor 3).

Stage 3 Group Performing: Sacrifice to the Group

During this period of time, every group members were cooperative working in assigned task, sacrifice for their work

became visible under the supervision of their instructor and instructor network support, as the following examples from student participants and instructors:

“...Learning to develop innovation was so complicated, one must dedicate oneself to do that, it was a group work. If our group was disunity, it was impossible to get work done. At first I was so worried, it was as I was told...but it was a group work, we must help. If it was an individual work, it was hard to accomplish. In planning to develop innovation, we had to have a backup plan, such as innovation number 1 and 2. If innovation number 1 couldn’t work, then number 2 would do. I thought it was useful. It made us extend our idea. It helped us to continue thinking and whatever we did... always had a backup plan” (A member no 3 of FGD no 2).

“We must brainstorm to fix the problem. It was a great period, I felt that we went together...like we were strong...(laughed)” (A member no 3 of FGD no 3).

“This course made everyone think, expressed their opinions, and planed...step forward...but at some point, we must be both leader and follower, we must be...we really did (sound like to cry, friends laughed)” (A member no 6 of FGD no 7).

“We spent time together, worked together, solved problem together, all more than 10 hours, it was the peak. We just got power point presentation slides at 1 am.” (A member no 4 of FGD no 8).

“I had to be a group leader, I had never done that before, had to make a decision, I would call this period “It was OK” to continue group work. Although we faced the problem, it was OK, thought that we must come up with the good solution, didn’t be stressed out... thought positive...” (A member no 5 of FGD no 9).

“My task was a facilitator, to calm their mind and warm their heart that I was always there when they needed. The problem that they could not solve I would direct or advice at all channels, such as line group, phone call, made an appointment, etc...I would be always available” (Instructor 2).

“Had group learning as adult learner, I gave an advice but they must dedicate themselves for group work, I supported them, they came and submitted their work according to schedule, if they would not follow as schedule, then I would discuss with them to find the solution” (Instructor 5).

Stage 4 Close Relationship: Being a Part of a Group

In this period, their group work was almost done, the innovation was pilot testing. The close relationship among group occurred because they worked closely for many hours a day, for several weeks, as the following examples from student participants and instructors:

“When we were a part of the group, we must adjust ourselves to the team, our personalities were difference, some had a short temper, some were a calm person. We learned how to know our friends

personalities by talking to everyone” (A member no 3 of FGD no 1).

“Adding...listening to the group ideas... It was very importance because some friends hardly listened to other ideas...They thought that their idea was absolutely right. I thought that listening to other was very importance, it helped to be able to continue working, we learned from friends. Friends had different experiences, had different skills, some were good at documents, some were good at making power point presentation slides, we learned from each other and taught each other” (A member no 6 of FGD no 4).

“We worked together more than 20 hours a day, we were so close and bound, we knew each other very well, we could consult not only about work but also the privacy ” (A member no 3 of FGD no 6).

“When students could adjust to cooperative working, I looked after them from some distance with our concern. They felt that they were some part of their group that could help to achieve goal” (Instructor 5).

“When flaming ignition occurred, they would dedicate to work. I just approved the work they submitted, this must hurry response, guided them how to improve their work, encouraged them to continue their work and responded every times. All of these represented my attention” (Instructor 9).

Stage 5 Group Celebrations: Being Proud of the Group Achievement

This was the last period that everyone prepared for oral presentation their innovation with their instructor support and encouragement. In this period, students summarized their learning experiences and wrote group work summary also, they were proud of their work that finally they could make it. They also addressed the ideas to develop innovation in the future, as the following examples from student participants and instructors:

“During orientation period we were so exciting, we thought whether this course would be useful or not, could it be done? Although we were working, it was doubtful. When we finished the innovation piece, it was still doubtful. But when we were pilot testing with the patients and they said it was very good. We realized that the innovation was good, what we had done was not wasteful, it was useful for others. When we looked back, this innovation was not useful for us because our body was normal. But when it was pilot testing with patients, it was useful for them. We were so proud.” (A member no 8 of FGD no 5).

“Passed this course I felt... Wow!!!...I was not the old-fashioned student anymore, I could create new thing that was useful for others” (A member no 9 of FGD no 2).

“This course had opened my eyes, I could see my potential. In the past years, we didn’t do like this.

This course let us create innovation, when we practiced... everyone had to pull out their potential. Someone didn’t know that they had a great potential” (A member no 6 of FGD no 3).

“...We were so proud of ourselves. Finally, we could make it, we were proud of our innovation. When we were pilot testing our innovation with the patients, they liked it and complimented us. It seemed like every things went well. We were so impressed, it was above our expectation. Our group members were OK and loved each other more.” (A member no 6 of FGD no 7).

“...We showed them that we were so proud of their work, especially in the presentation session, their presentation was compared with other groups we had to encourage them until the last minute.” (Instructor 3).

“We encouraged them, we were very proud of them that they worked until their goal was achieved. Whether they won the prize in their work or not, it appeared that they cooperatively worked until the difficult work was done, they got over the hump together.” (Instructor 7).

VIII. DISCUSSION

The focus group data collection, analysis undertaken with 76 senior students for 9 groups, as well as in-depth interviews with nine group instructors represent a teaching and learning process of group working in the nursing innovation project course at KKU. In turn this discussion examines the process further and envisions related implications in other similar context. Our findings suggest the potential of the synthesized small group working teaching-learning process as an approach to creating effective learning outcome for students in the context of passive and silent culture. These findings are consistent with other studies of effective teaching strategies for Asian students (See Bray, 2009; Lee, Lee, 2012; Yuce, Sahin, Kocer, Kana, 2013). In Thai cultural context, people are taught to be humble and respect to the elders, they don’t like to express their opinion in public. Despite being as a new generation of the Thai context and culture, the student participants acknowledged to maintain “*Kreng Jai*” by being calm when they are facing an unfamiliar or superior person like an instructor, they would sit quietly and listen passively. It may be that the Thai students think that they will disturb other people when they speak out, or they are too shy to express their opinions. Therefore, this issue might be the vital obstacle factor in designing teaching learning and innovation development which needs students who are active learners, think outside the box, creativity, making a difference, emerging new thought leading to the ideas to create new product, new service and new process. Researchers had designed implementing group work learning to decrease the limitations of the learning culture of Thai society (Hughes, Jones, 2011). To explore the innovation, there were 5 important skills, including 1) connecting knowledge and new ideas, 2) questioning nursing phenomena, 3) observing nursing phenomena, 4) expecting the interaction between nursing

phenomena and invented innovation, and 5) testing the innovation. Emergence of creativity, students must dare to do new things; take risk wisely in changing; be enthusiastic in questioning, observing, interacting, and frequent testing (Macgowan, Vakharia, 2012). Although student participants in this study were anxious to cringe and groan when told that they had to work in a group to develop nursing innovation. Finally, group work had shown to be good for students.

The study results confirmed that group work active learning was achieved, students' learning was improved and actively involved in the group process (Macgowan, Vakharia, 2012; Chiriac, 2014). With the sufficient education resources support and guidance, students could overcome undesirable conditions and disadvantages for group work and potential pitfalls. Based on group process helped members to share their experiences and abilities in problem solving (Wondo, Mei, Seto, 2018; Kuh, Kinzie, Buckley, Bridges, Hayek, 2006).

However, the study showed that group work learning method had limitation and challenge to the future. The most difficult period student participants reported was the agreement of which innovation they wanted to create. There were pressures from the group to conform to the majority opinion. It may be because of their personalities in Thai context that they did not like to have a conflict and attempted to avoid it when possible. The study results also revealed that in some group there was an individual member dominating the discussion and other members were not gaining satisfaction from the group. Some members might rely too heavily on others to do the work. Some members did not pitch in, help, or adequately contribute to the group (Freeman and Greenacre, 2011). To lower the limitations of using group work learning method, arrangement of activities cultivating a good moral in cooperative working to achieve its goals is recommended. Goals accomplishment is a group achievement, assigning tasks for each member to be responsible for must be equally distributed among the group (Gegenfurtner, Hagenauer, 2013).

Study Limitations

Although students were interviewed and discussed within a group where they felt comfortable in the conference room, the procedures took place in the faculty. This may have hampered student participants' comfort in divulging experiences or beliefs that might be at odds with the research assistants who may have been viewed as an instructor's representative or critical of the instructors. Steps were taken to increase their confidence in the confidentiality of their stories; for example, instructors were not involved in the data collection of this study. There were several strengths to this study. First, students were randomly assigned to different discussed groups. This approach ensured that this study captured the range of experiences of students when learning in group work and there was no barrier to mention about other members of the group in negative ways. Second, the research assistants were also student status and from the same cultural background as the student participants and thus understood and could explore nuanced verbal and nonverbal communication.

IX. CONCLUSIONS

Thai students may be reluctant to express their opinions in a classroom, which they think that this might bother teachers or other unfamiliar people, partly due to the core Thai cultural value of *Kreng Jai*. Like students from other Asian countries, Thai students were familiar with silent in a classroom. The results from this study, teaching learning strategy by group working to develop the ideas of nursing innovation, should be integrated into knowledge translation studies aimed at improving teaching learning for Thai students and other similar context.

REFERENCE

- [1] R.S. Baron, N.L. Kerr, "Group process, group decision, group action, Maidenhead: Open University Press", 2003.
- [2] L. Bray, "Cultural dimensions for a foreigner teaching English in a Thai university", *TESOL in context*, Special ed., Issue S2, pp. 1-109.
- [3] J. Brennan, S. Ryan, M. Ranga, S. Broek, N. Durazzi, B. Kamphuis, "Study on innovation in higher education: final report", Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2014.
- [4] P. Brysiewicz, R. Cassimjee, P. McInerney, "An exploratory survey of undergraduate nursing students' experiences of group work within a Problem-Based Curriculum", *Curationis*, Issue Nov., pp. 12-20, 2002.
- [5] P. Burnard, W. Naiyapatana, "Culture and Communication in Thai Nursing: A Report of an Ethnographic Study", *IJNS.*, Vol. 41, pp. 755-765, 2004.
- [6] E.H. Chiriac, K. Granström, "Teachers' leadership and students' experience of group work", *Teachers and Teaching: theory and practice*, Vol. 18, Issue 3, pp. 345-363, 2012.
- [7] E.H. Chiriac, "Group work as an incentive for learning- students' experiences of group work", *Front. Psychol.*, Vol.5, pp. 558, 2014.
- [8] J. Cho, A. Trent, "Validity in qualitative research", *QR*, Vol. 6, pp. 319-340, 2006.
- [9] J. Cummings, "Chiang Mai and Northern Thailand: Gateway to Thailand's colourful north", Melbourne, Vic: Lonely Planet Publications, 2002.
- [10] P.L. Curseu, H. Pluut, "Student groups as learning entities: the effect of group diversity and teamwork quality on groups' cognitive complexity", *Stud. High. Educ.*, Vol. 38, pp. 87-103, 2013.
- [11] L. Freeman, L. Greenacre, "An examination of socially destructive behaviors in group work", *J Market Educ.*, Vol. 33, Issue 1, 5-17, 2011.
- [12] A. Gegenfurtner, G. Hagenauer, "Achievement goals and achievement goal orientations in education", *Int J Educ Res.*, Vol. 61, Issue 1, pp. 1-4, 2013.
- [13] A. Hébert, P. Hauf, "Student learning through service learning: Effects on academic development, civic responsibility, interpersonal skills and practical skills", *Active Learn. High. Educ.*, Vol. 16, Issue 1, pp. 37-49, 2015.
- [14] R.L. Hughes, S.K. Jones, "Developing and assessing college student teamwork skills", *NDIR.*, Vol. 149, pp. 53-64, 2011.
- [15] D. Jongudomkam, P. Forgeron, P. Siripul P, A. Finley, "My Child You Must Have Patience and Kreng Jai: Thai Parents and Child Pain", *J. Nurs. Scholarsh.*, Vol. 44, Issue 4, pp. 323-331, 2012.
- [16] D. Jongudomkam, "Handbook of the nursing innovation project course", Khon Kaen: Faculty of Nursing, Khon Kaen University, 2016.
- [17] D. Jongudomkam, R. Phupaibul, R. Kumhom, C. Tejagupta, C. Wacharasin, W. Deoisres, "Perceptions of the Thai family well-being: A qualitative study", *Journal of Nursing Sciences and Health*, Vol. 40, Issue 1, pp. 14-29, 2017 (In Thai).
- [18] G.D. Kuh, J. Kinzie, J.A. Buckley, B.K. Bridges, J.C. Hayek, "What Matters to Student Success: A Review of the Literature", *NPEC*. 21/9/2016, http://nces.ed.gov/npec/pdf/kuh_team_report.pdf
- [19] C. Kayrooz, C. Trevitt, "Research in organisations and communities: Tales from the real world", Crows Nest: Allen and Unwin, 2006.
- [20] H.J. Lee, J. Lee, "Who gets the best grades at top universities? An exploratory analysis of institution-wide interviews with the highest achievers at a top Korean University", *Asia Pacific Educ. Rev.*, Vol. 13, pp. 665-676, 2012.

- [21] M.J. Macgowan, S.P. Vakharia, "Teaching Standards-Based Group Work Competencies to Social Work Students: An Empirical Examination", *Res. Soc. Work.*, Vol. 22, Issue 4, pp. 380-388, 2012.
- [22] A.L. Marterella, M. Rebecca, R.M. Aldrich, "Developing occupational therapy students' practice habits via qualitative inquiry education", *Can. J. Occup. Ther.*, Vol. 82, Issue 2, pp. 119-28, 2015.
- [23] K. McKinney, M.D. Day, "A Multi-institutional Study of Students' Perceptions and Experiences in the Research based Capstone Course in Sociology", *Teach. Sociol.*, Vol. 40, Issue 2, pp. 142-57, 2012.
- [24] D.C. Mugot, E.B. Sumbalan, "The 21st Century Learning Skills and Teaching Practices of Pre-Service Teachers: Implication to the New Philippine Teacher Education Curriculum", *IJMRAP*, Volume 2, Issue 1, pp. 22-28, 2019.
- [25] M.H. Murray, B. Lonne, "An innovative use of the web to build graduate team skills", *Teach. High. Educ.*, Vol. 1, Issue 11, pp. 3-77, 2006.
- [26] Office for National Economic and Social Development Board (NESDB), "National Economic and Social Development Plan Number (NESDP) 12 (2017-2021)", Bangkok: Office of the Prime Minister, 2017 (in Thai).
- [27] Office for National Economic and Social Development Board (NESDB), "Report the information of Thailand", Retrieved Jan 12, 2019, From: http://social.nesdb.go.th/SocialStat/StatDefault_Final.aspx.
- [28] D.F. Polit, B.P. Hungler, "Essentials of nursing research: Methods, appraisal, and utilization", 8th ed., Philadelphia: Wolters Kluwer/Lippincott Williams and Wilkins, 2013.
- [29] P. Schwartz-Shea, D. Yanow, "Interpretive research design: concepts and processes", New York and London: Routledge, 2012.
- [30] C. Senior, C. Howard, "Learning in friendship group: developing students' conceptual understanding through social interaction", *Front. Psychol.*, Vol. 5, pp. 1031, 2014.
- [31] P. Serdyukov, "Innovation in education: what works, what doesn't, and what to do about it?", *JRIT&L.*, Vol. 10, Issue 1, pp. 4-33, 2017.
- [32] H.J. Streubert, D.R. Carpenter, "Qualitative Research in Nursing Advancing the Humanistic Imperative", Philadelphia: Wolters Kluwer, 2011.
- [33] S. Supab, "Thai society and culture values: Family & tradition", Bangkok: Thai Wattana Panich Publishing, 1994, (in Thai).
- [34] The Office of Khon Kaen Public Relations, "Khon Kaen University prospectuses 2018", Khon Kaen: The KKU Office of Public Relation, 2018.
- [35] H. Winlow, D. Simm, R. Schaaf, A. Marvell, "Using focus group research to support teaching and learning", *JGHE*, Vol. 37, Issue 2, pp. 292-303, 2012.
- [36] M. Woods, M.E. Rosenberg, "Educational Tools: Thinking Outside the Box", *Clin J Am Soc Nephrol.*, Vol. 11, Issue 3, pp. 518-526, 2016.
- [37] M.T.S. Wondo, M.F. Mei, S.B. Seto, "The Impact of Search, Solve, Create and Share Model on the Motivation and Mathematic's Achievement of the Students Grade Eight in Detukeli State JHS," *IJMRAP*, Volume 1, Issue 6, pp. 1-4, 2018.
- [38] B. Wyatt, S. Promkandorn, "A discourse analysis of the Thai experience of *being krengjai*" *Intercult. Pragmat.*, Vol. 9, Issue 3, pp. 363-85, 2012.
- [39] K. Yuce, E.Y. Sahin, O.M. Kocer, E. Kana, "Motivations for choosing teaching as a career: a perspective of pre-service teachers from a Turkish context", *Asia Pacific Educ. Rev.*, Vol. 14, pp. 295-306, 2013.